

**Using wireless rumen sensors for evaluating the effects of diet and ambient temperature
in nonlactating dairy goats**

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Abstract

Sixteen multiparous non-lactating Murciano-Granadina dairy goats, provided with wireless telemetric rumen sensors of pH and temperature (KB1001 Kahne bolus), were used in 2 consecutive experiments to assess ruminal variations produced by rations with different forage:concentrate ratio (Exp. 1) and to monitor the effects of heat stress (HS) on the rumen environment (Exp. 2). Goats were subjected to ruminal surgery to insert the rumen boluses programmed to record and store rumen pH and temperature every 30 min. In Exp. 1, 8 goats (38.6 ± 2.3 kg BW) were divided into 2 groups and fed 2 isonitrogenous rations varying in the

forage to concentrate ratio (HF, high forage 70:30; LF, low forage 30:70) according to a crossover design, consisting of 2 periods of 19 d and 4 goats each. Diets and water were offered once-daily at 1130 (for 4 h) and 1745 (for 30 min), respectively. Rectal temperatures were recorded 3 times daily (0900, 1300 and 1700). Ruminal pH was greater ($+0.31 \pm 0.06$; $P < 0.001$) in the HF than LF. No rectal and ruminal temperature differences were detected between treatments (38.2 ± 0.1 and $38.9 \pm 0.1^\circ\text{C}$ on average, respectively). There was a high positive correlation between ruminal and rectal temperatures ($r = 0.91$; $P < 0.001$). Rumen temperature decreased by 3.5°C after drinking, and 2 h were needed to return to the average values. In Exp. 2, 8 goats (43.9 ± 1.0 kg BW) were kept in metabolic cages, fed a 50:50 forage to concentrate diet, and exposed to 2 ambient temperatures. Experimental design was a crossover with 2 periods of 21 d and 4 goats each. Climatic conditions were: 1) thermal neutral (TN, 20 to 23 $^\circ\text{C}$ day-night), and 2) heat stress (HS, 12-h day at 37 $^\circ\text{C}$ and 12-h night at 30 $^\circ\text{C}$). Humidity was $40 \pm 5\%$ and light-dark cycles were 12-12 h. Feed was offered once daily and feed intake was recorded daily. Water was freely available at ambient temperature. Rectal temperature and respiratory rate were daily recorded (0900, 1300 and 1700 h). Although both goat groups had similar DMI, rumen pH was 0.12 units lower ($P < 0.01$) in HS than in TN. In contrary, rumen temperature ($+0.30^\circ\text{C}$), rectal temperature ($+0.4^\circ\text{C}$), respiratory rate ($+77$ breathes/min), and water consumption ($+3.2$ L/d) were greater ($P < 0.01$) in HS than in TN. In conclusion, wireless boluses have been proved to be useful tool to monitor rumen pH and temperature as affected by different management and climatic conditions. Despite the same feed intake, rumen pH was lower by high ambient temperature, which might indicate an altered microbial fermentation under heat stress conditions.

INTRODUCTION

Continuous readings by telemetry help in measuring responses dynamically and defining associations with different management and environmental variables (Eigenberg et al., 2008; Rutten et al., 2013). By the use of wireless telemetric rumen boluses for temperature measurement, significant effects of estrus and parturition (Cooper-Prado et al., 2011), bovine viral diarrhea infection (Rose-Dye et al., 2010), SARA (Alzahal et al., 2009), and intramammary injection of LPS (Alzahal et al., 2011) on rumen temperature have been reported.

Changes in ambient temperature provoke different responses in the nervous, circulatory, respiratory, renal and endocrine systems, which allow the animal to cope with the altered environment. Different physiological, lactational, and nutritional responses to heat stress (**HS**) have been reported in dairy cows (Baumgard and Rhoads, 2013) and goats (Hamzaoui et al., 2013; Salama et al., 2013). However, little is known about ruminal changes in pH and temperature due to HS in dairy animals.

When feed intake was held constant in hot and thermo-neutral environments, HS reduced the concentration of VFA in the rumen of cattle (Kelly et al., 1967), increased the concentration of lactic acid, and reduced ruminal pH (Mishra et al., 1970). Moreover, profiling the bacterial species composition of rumen fluid using 16sRNA gene cloning revealed that HS resulted in consistent changes in microbial diversity, reduced VFA concentrations and an overall lowering of rumen pH in heifers (Tajima et al., 2007). To our knowledge, rumen biosensors have not been used in goats to continuously measure changes in ruminal environment under HS conditions.

The objective of the current study was to evaluate the use of ruminal biosensors to assess ruminal variations produced by rations with different forage:concentrate ratio and to monitor

the effects of HS on the rumen environment of non-lactating goats. To avoid the confusion between reduced DMI and HS effects, both thermo-neutral and HS non-lactating goats were kept at the same level of feed intake to meet maintenance requirements.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The treatment procedures and animal care conditions were reviewed and approved by the Ethical Committee on Animal and Human Experimentation of the Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona (reference CEEAH 11/1166) and the codes of recommendations for the welfare of livestock of the Ministry of Agriculture, Food and Environment of Spain.

Description, Calibration, and Insertion of the Wireless Ruminal boluses

Wireless telemetric rumen boluses (Model KB1001; Kahne Ltd, Auckland, New Zealand) designed for animals >300 kg BW were used for rumen pH and temperature recording. The recording system included: rumen boluses (27 mm in diameter, 145 mm in height, and 70 g in weight), top receiver for capturing the data signals sent by the boluses (frequency: 433.9 MHz), field receiver with yagi antenna (frequency: 400-500 MHz), Kahne wand (trigger device for transmitting the data to the storage device through RFID), a software (Kahne Data Processing System V.5.2.4) for enabling the configuration and communication between boluses and the transceiver via a computer, and magnet blocker (to turn on and off boluses). Boluses were manufactured to measure temperature in a range of 0 to 45°C (accuracy ± 0.8 °C) and pH 4.00 to 8.00 (accuracy ± 0.02).

The calibration process was done before each experiment according to the manufacturer instructions using deionized water at 40 ± 0.5 °C for temperature calibration and pH buffer solutions of 4.01 and 7.00 (Crison Instruments SA, Barcelona, Spain) for pH calibration. Before the insertion into the rumen, boluses were configured to record rumen pH and

temperature values every 30 min throughout the experiment with 2 downloads at the start and end of each period in each experiment.

Given the low size and weight of goats, boluses were inserted through a ruminal incision. For the ruminal surgery, goats were anaesthetized by the i.m. injection of 0.3 mL of xilacina (50 mg/mL; Bayer Hispania, Barcelona, Spain) and 1 mL ketamina (50 mg/mL; Holliday Scott, Sant Isidro, Argentina). After shaving, an incision of 10-12 cm was done in the left flank (between the last rib and the ischial tuberosity). After setting out the rumen, a rumenotomy of 8 cm was done and the bolus was introduced into the rumen with the wings folded and tied to prevent damage to the rumen wall. After rumen wall, muscle layer and skin have been sutured, 2 mL of an anti-inflammatory (20 mg/ml; Metacam, Boehringer Ingelheim, Barcelona, Spain) and 4 mL of an antibiotic (1.5 mg/mL; Invemox, Invesa, Barcelona, Spain;) were i.m. injected for 5 d.

Experiment 1

Animals, management conditions, and treatments

Eight multiparous non-lactating Murciano-Granadina goats (38.6 ± 2.3 kg BW) were used from the flock of the Experimental Farm of the Servei de Granges i Camps Experiments (SGCE) of the Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona (Bellaterra, Barcelona, Spain). Goats were kept in a confinement system, where they were maintained indoors in straw bedded pens and each animal individually received food and water. Minimum and maximum environmental temperatures averaged 10.0 ± 0.4 and 16.2 ± 0.5 °C, respectively in the experimental barn throughout the experiment.

Goats were allowed 17-d recovery period after boluses insertion by surgery. The experimental design was a crossover with 2 treatments in 2 periods, lasting 19 d, and 4 goats each. Goats were switched to the opposite treatment in the second period with a 3 d of gradual

shift to the new diet. The treatments were 2 diets with different forage:concentrate ratio: high forage (**HF**; 70:30) and low forage (**LF**; 30:70). Dehydrated fescue hay and barley were used to formulate diets that cover the maintenance requirements according to INRA (2007). The diet was daily offered at 1130 h and withdrew at 1530 h, whereas water was offered at 1745 h for 30 min. Goats had free access to mineral-vitamin blocks.

Sampling, measurements, and analyses

Data were collected during the last 7 d of each period. Samples of feed ingredients were taken at the start of the experiment and, diets andorts were daily sampled, composited and stored at 4°C until analysis. Feed intake and water consumption were daily recorded. The samples were ground through a 1 mm stainless steel screen for the determination of DM, NDF and ADF according to AOAC (2003).

The DM was determined at 103°C for 24 h and then samples were burnt in a muffle furnace at 550°C for 4 h to measure the ash content. The CP was analyzed according to the Dumas method for N determination using a Leco analyzer (Leco Corporation, St. Joseph, MI). The NDF and ADF were determined using an Ankom200 Fiber Analyzer incubator (Ankom Technology, Macedon, NY) adding amylase and sodium sulphite solutions. Chemical composition and nutritive value of the ration ingredients are shown in Table 5.1.

Daily rectal temperatures were measured at 0900, 1300, and 1700 h by a digital clinical thermometer (Model mini color, ICO Technology, Barcelona, Spain; range, 32.0 to 43.9°C; accuracy, $\pm 0.1^\circ\text{C}$). Urine was individually collected at the last day of each period before feeding and pH was measured using a portable pH-meter (pH25, Crison Instruments, Barcelona, Spain) within 1 h after collection.

Table 1 Chemical composition and nutritive value (DM basis) of the ration ingredients used for non-lactating goats.

Item	Exp. 1		Exp. 2	
	Fescue hay	Barley	Alfalfa hay	Barley
Component, %				
DM	91.7	91.0	88.6	89.5
OM	88.3	97.1	87.4	97.4
CP	10.7	9.6	20.0	10.8
NDF	55.4	17.7	36.7	16.4
ADF	32.5	5.9	27.0	6.1
Nutritive value ¹				
UEm/kg ²	1.30	–	0.90	–
UFL/kg ³	0.72	1.05	0.72	1.06
NE _L , Mcal/kg	1.22	1.79	1.22	1.80
PDIE ⁴ , g/kg	77	95	101	98
PDIN ⁵ , g/kg	67	66	128	74
PDIA ⁶ , g/kg	28	28	56	32
Ca, g/kg	4.5	0.8	16.7	0.8
P, g/kg	3.0	4.0	2.3	4.0

¹Calculated according to INRA (2007).

²Fill units for sheep (1 UEm = 1 kg DM reference grass).

³Feed units for maintenance (1 UFL = 1.7 Mcal EN_L).

⁴Protein digested in the small intestine supplied by microbial protein from rumen-fermented organic matter.

⁵Protein digested in the small Intestine supplied by microbial protein from rumen-degraded protein.

⁶Protein digested in the small Intestine supplied by rumen-undegraded dietary protein.

Experiment 2

Animals, management conditions, and treatments

Eight Murciano-Granadina non-lactating goats (43.9 ± 1.0 kg BW) from the Experimental Farm of the SGCE were used. The experimental design was a crossover with 2 treatments in 2 periods, lasting 21 d, and 4 goats each. Goats were switched to the opposite treatment in the second period. Treatment conditions were: 1) thermal neutral (TN; 20 to 23°C and 45%; THI = 65 to 68), and 2) heat stress (HS; from 900 to 2100 h at 37 °C and 40%; THI = 85; and from 2100 to 900 h at 30 °C and 40%; THI = 77). The THI values were calculated according to NRC (1971) as follows: $THI = (1.8 \times T_{db} + 32) - [(0.55 - 0.0055 \times RH) \times (1.8 \times T_{db} - 26.8)]$.

Throughout the experiment, (June to July), the TN goats were kept indoors and the temperature was maintained at 20 to 23°C with the help of air conditioning system (Summit-Serie E10; Hitachi, Barcelona, Spain). The HS goats were kept in a 4×6×2.3 m climatic chamber (Euroshield, ETS Lindgren-Euroshield Oy, Eura, Finland) provided with a temperature and humidity controlling system (CAREL Controls Iberica, Barcelona, Spain). A continuous 90 m³/h air turnover was maintained throughout the experiment.

Goats had a 1-wk pre-experimental period for the recovery from the ruminal surgery and for the adaptation to diet and metabolic cages. When goats were switched from TN to HS conditions, a transition period of 2 d was allowed (1 d at 25°C and 1 d at 30°C), but no transition was applied for the change from HS to TN. Photoperiod was maintained constant at 12-12 h light-dark (0900 to 2100 h).

Goats fed a ration (forage:concentrate ratio = 50:50) to cover their maintenance requirements according to INRA (2007). The ration consisted of (as fed) dehydrated alfalfa hay (1.22 Mcal of NEL/kg and 20.0% CP; DM basis) and concentrate (1.80 Mcal NEL /kg,

10.8% CP, DM basis). The amount of feed was individually calculated in accordance with the BW. Mineralized salt blocks were freely available in each metabolic cage (Composition: Na, 36.74%; Ca, 0.32; Mg, 1.09%; Zn, 5 g/kg; Mn, 1.5 g/kg; S, 912 mg/kg; Fe, 304 mg/kg; I, 75 mg/kg; Co, 50 mg/kg; Se, 25 mg/kg; Ovi bloc, Sal Cupido, Terrasa, Spain). Clean water was freely available at ambient temperature for each treatment.

Measurements, sampling, and analyses

Rectal temperatures and respiration rates were daily recoded at 0900, 1300 and 1700 h. The rectal temperature was measured with the same digital clinical thermometer used in Exp. 1. The respiration rate was measured by counting the inhalations and exhalations for 60 s with the aid of a chronometer.

Feed was offered once a day at 1200 h and water consumption (accuracy, ± 20 g) were recorded daily throughout the experimental period. Trays with saw dust were put below the drinking troughs and weighted twice daily to take into account water wastes. Feed samples were collected before the beginning of each experimental period and were analysed as for Exp. 1.

Feed orts were daily collected, weighed, and composited for analysis. Feces of each goat were daily collected and 10% of fresh feces were dried at 60°C for 48 h. Then a composited sample for each goat was stored at room temperature until analysis. Orts, feces, and fecal samples were ground through a 1 mm stainless steel screen and then analyzed for DM, CP, ADF, NDF (AOAC, 2003).

Blood samples (approximately 0.3 mL) were collected before feeding only at the end of the second period by using insulin syringes (1 mL BD Micro-Fine, BD Medical-Diabetes Care, Franklin Lakes, NJ). A single drop of blood was applied to disposable cartridges containing biochemical and silicon chip technology (i-STAT EC8+, Abbott Point of Care,

Princeton, NJ). Then, the cartridge was inserted into an i-STAT handheld analyzer, and the results of glucose, urea, Cl, Na, K, total CO₂ concentration, anion gap, hematocrit, hemoglobin, pH, partial pressure of CO₂, HCO₃⁻, and base excess were obtained.

Statistical Analyses

Data were analyzed by the PROC MIXED for repeated measurements of SAS version 9.1.3 (SAS Inst. Inc., Cary, North Carolina, USA). The statistical mixed model used for both experiments contained the fixed effect of treatment (HF vs. LF or TN vs. HS), day (1 to 7) and period (1 and 2); the random effect of the animal; interaction between treatment and day and between treatment and period; and the residual error.

Data of rumen temperature and rumen pH were averaged for the 7-d measurement period and the fixed effect of the day hour was included in the model rather than the day effect. Data of digestibility and blood measures (Exp. 2) were analyzed by ANOVA using PROC GLM of SAS. The model contained the effect of treatment and period; the interaction between treatment and period; and the residual error. Models took into account the possible carryover effects of previous treatment period through the interaction between treatment and period. Moreover, data of Exp. 1 were used for the construction of sigmoidal curves to summarize daily ruminal pH records using calculated time below (min/d) as the y-variate and pH cutoff point as the x-variate.

Differences between least squares means were determined with the PDIFF option of SAS. Pearson's correlations were used to determine the relationship between the studied variables. Significance was declared as $P < 0.05$, unless otherwise indicated, and tendencies were discussed at $P < 0.10$.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

At the end of each experiment, boluses were surgically recovered and they were found in the ventral sac. After boluses recovering, drifts from the initial values were calculated using pH standard solutions 4.01 and 7.00. The overall drifts for both experiments were small and averaged and 0.01 ± 0.02 and -0.02 ± 0.02 for pH 4.01 and 7.00, respectively. These results indicate that sensors were measuring accurately throughout experiments, which agrees with the findings of Mullins et al. (2012) and Hassanat et al. (2013). We did not compare between rumen pH measured by sensors and traditional pH meters, but in previous research works, a significant relationship was detected between measures by the 2 methods in cows ($r = 0.59$; Lohölter et al., 2013) and sheep ($r = 0.46$; Kaur et al. (2010) fed rations with different forage:concentrate ratios.

Experiment 1

Feed intake and water consumption

In the current study, HF and LF goats were fed at the maintenance level, and no differences were detected in DMI or water consumption (Table 2). Giger-Reverdin et al. (2011) proposed an equation to estimate total water intake (TWI) in dairy goats in temperate climate: $TWI \text{ L/d} = 0.0892 \text{ BW kg} + 0.673 \text{ Milk production L/d}$. Average TWI value estimated by this equation (38.6 kg BW and zero milk production) was 3.44 L/d, and the actual consumption averaged 3.90 L/d plus 0.07 L from food (actual TWI = 3.97 L/d), which is +15% of the estimated value.

Ruminal pH and temperatures

Mean pH value for HF diet was greater than for the LF diet (Table 2). Similarly, Cantalapiedra-Hijar et al. (2009) reported lower ruminal pH values measured by pH meter in

Granadina goats when fed 70% concentrate (6.26) compared to 70% forage (6.43) diets due to a greater concentration of lactic acid concentration when the proportion of concentrate increased in the diet.

We are not aware of previous studies measured rumen pH over 24 h with short time intervals (i.e. every 30 min) in goats. Rumen pH in LF goats was lower ($P < 0.01$) than in HF goats at all time points except from 9 to 14 h after feeding (Figure 5.6). The pattern of pH curve varied according to the diet. For the HF diet, there was a linear slow descending phase until 12.5 h post feeding (pH decreased by 0.37 units; $y = 6.58 - 0.02x$, $R^2 = 0.86$; $P < 0.01$) followed by a linear ascending phase until 24 h ($y = 5.83 + 0.04x$, $R^2 = 0.99$; $P < 0.001$). On the other hand, pH rapidly decreased by 0.50 units during the first 6 h after feeding in LF goats ($y = 6.36 - 0.05x$, $R^2 = 0.79$; $P < 0.01$), linearly increased from 6.5 to 9 h ($y = 5.63 + 0.07x$, $R^2 = 0.96$; $P < 0.001$), steadied from 9.5 to 18 h, and finally increased until 24 h ($y = 5.19 + 0.06x$, $R^2 = 0.98$; $P < 0.001$). Mishra et al. (1970) reported that a high roughage diet induces a delayed microbial fermentation compared to a concentrate diet, which agrees with the slower reduction in rumen pH observed in our HF compared to LF diet. The increase in rumen pH after 12 h (HF goats) and 18 h (LF goats) post-feeding could be due the accumulation of saliva in the rumen during rumination.

It is also possible to study the rumen pH by measuring the amount of time spent below pH cut-off points, thus adding more accuracy to the interpretation of ruminal pH data. AlZahal et al. (2007) proposed such ruminal pH models using logistic curves. A sigmoidal shaped curve was generated by plotting the accumulated time spent below (y-variable, 0 to 1440 min/d) each pH point (x-variable, pH 5.9 to 7.0) for both diets (Figure 5.7). The inflection points on pH curves were 6.51 at 735 min and 6.26 at 773 min for HF and LF diets, respectively. These inflection values were very close to actual pH averages reported in Table 5.2. Despite differences between diets and rumen pH, the slope of curves was similar.

Rumen temperature values averaged $38.9 \pm 0.1^\circ\text{C}$ and no differences were detected between HF and LF diets throughout the experiment (Table 5.2). These results are contrary to those of AlZahal et al. (2009; 2011), Wahrmund et al. (2012), and Lohölter et al. (2013) who reported greater rumen temperature with high concentrate diets in cattle. Heat is considered a byproduct of microbial fermentation (Hungate, 1966) and, therefore, concentrates are expected to generate more heat within the rumen during a given period of time post-feeding than forage diets. In the current study, no goat had rumen pH below 5.6 (SARA limit in cattle) at any time point, indicating normal conditions in the rumen. Only 4 LF goats had pH values slightly lower than 6.00 ($\text{pH} = 5.94 \pm 0.03$ for 105 ± 45 min). On the other hand, the previous studies, in which rumen temperature was affected by diet, indicated lower rumen pH values than 5.6 (AlZahal et al., 2009; 2011). The differences in rumen temperature between treatments could be also tested as the durations (min/d) above specific thresholds. AlZahal et al. (2011) suggested that the threshold 38.8°C could be of a diagnostic significance for the detection of SARA in nonfebrile dairy cows. Neither this threshold (38.8°C) nor other greater thresholds (39.2 and 39.6°C) varied between LF and HF goats in our study (Table 5.2).

Nevertheless, rumen temperature increased ($P < 0.001$) by 0.82 and 1.25°C at 30 and 60 min after feeding, respectively, due to the increase in fermentation activity. Rumen temperature remained elevated until the time of water drinking, when rumen temperature fell by 3.42 and 3.51°C ($P < 0.001$) at 30 and 60 min after drinking (Figure 5.6). Values of rumen temperature were recovered and were similar ($P = 0.645$) to the pre-feeding values at 2 h after drinking. Then, rumen temperatures gradually increased and were greater ($P < 0.05$) than the pre-feeding value, but never reached the pre-drinking values because feed was restricted and no new feed was introduced into the digestive system after drinking. During the last 3.5 h before the following meal, rumen temperature decreased in accordance with the reduction in

ambient temperature and were similar ($P = 0.135$ to 0.812) to those of pre-feeding values (Figure 6).

Our goats drank on average 3.9 ± 0.7 L of cold water (9.8 ± 0.4 °C) within 5 to 10 min. The decrease in rumen temperature after drinking in the current study (-3.4 °C at 30 min) was much lower than that reported by Bewley et al. (2008) in dairy cows (-8.5 °C at 15 min) drenched 25 L of cold water (7.6 °C). In the later study, rumen temperature recovered at 3.5 h after water drenching, but in our results values returned to normal range by 2 h. It should be taken into account that boluses in the study of Bewley et al. (2008) were located in the reticulum, whereas in our goats boluses were in the ventral sac, which might explain differences in the magnitude of temperature reduction after drinking. We detected a positive correlation ($r = 0.59$; $P < 0.05$) between the amount of water drunk (2.6 to 5.8 L) and the decrease in rumen temperature (-2.4 to -5.6 °C) at 30 min after water consumption.

Because rumen temperature increased and rumen pH decreased after feeding, there was a negative correlation ($r = 0.33$; $P < 0.05$) between both parameters in the current study, which agrees with what reported by Wahrmund et al. (2012) and Lohölter et al. (2013). This inverse relationship between rumen pH and rumen temperature could be used to predict the rumen pH as previously indicated by AlZahal et al. (2009). Rumen temperature has been used for the detection of SARA in dairy cows (AlZahal et al., 2011).

Rectal temperature and relationship with ruminal temperature

In the current study, rectal temperature was measured at -2.5 , $+2.0$ and $+5.5$ h relative to feeding time. No differences were detected between both groups in rectal temperature (Table 5.2), but the values increased ($P < 0.01$) by time (37.5 , 38.4 , 38.8 °C at 0900, 1300, and 1700 h, respectively) because of heat produced after feeding and in accordance with the elevation in the ambient temperature throughout the day (from 10 to 16°C). In accordance, AlZahal et al. (2011) observed no effect of diet on vaginal temperature.

Rumen temperatures were on average $0.92 \pm 0.06^{\circ}\text{C}$ greater than rectal temperatures due to microbial fermentation, and increased ($P < 0.001$) by time (38.2, 39.5, and 39.6°C at 900, 1300, and 1700 h, respectively). Consequently, a high correlation ($r = 0.91$; $P < 0.001$) was detected between both rectal and ruminal temperatures.

Table 2 Feed and water intakes, rectal temperature, rumen temperature, rumen pH, and urine pH in non-lactating dairy goats fed diets containing 70% forage (HF; $n = 8$) or 30% forage (LF; $n = 8$). Values are least squares means and SE of the difference.

Item	Diet			Effect ($P =$)		
	HF	LF	SED	Treatment	Period	T \times P ¹
Daily intake						
DM, g	871	786	77	0.323	0.783	0.378
CP, g	104	90	9	0.170	0.897	0.385
NDF, g	446	263	38	0.005	0.983	0.456
ADF, g	246	126	21	0.003	0.952	0.488
NE _L , Mcal						
Water, L	3.72	4.07	0.96	0.728	0.228	0.878
Rectal temperature, $^{\circ}\text{C}$	38.22	38.16	0.13	0.660	0.161	0.464
Rumen temperature						
Average, $^{\circ}\text{C}$	38.82	38.92	0.12	0.396	0.156	0.783
≥ 38.8 , min/d ²	908	938	126	0.851	0.659	0.606
≥ 39.2 , min/d ²	548	540	150	0.968	0.680	0.266
≥ 39.6 , min/d ²	305	120	162	0.458	0.607	0.980
Rumen pH	6.56	6.25	0.06	0.001	0.048	0.001
Urine pH	7.65	7.67	0.20	0.923	0.063	0.552

¹Interaction Treatment \times Period

Figure 1. Rumen pH (\circ and \bullet) and rumen temperature (Δ and \blacktriangle) of non-lactating goats fed 70% forage (\circ , Δ ; $n = 10$) or 30% forage (\bullet , \blacktriangle ; $n = 10$). The solid arrow indicates time of feed withdrawal and the open arrow indicates dinking time. The SEM values were 0.03 and 0.13 for rumen pH and temperature, respectively.

Figure 2. pH curves of high (○) and low (●) forage diets. The y-axis represents the accumulated time (min/d) spent below each corresponding pH point on the x-axis. Dashed lines represent slopes of pH curves.

Experiment 2

Feed intake

Goats had no differences in DMI between TN and HS goats (Table 5.3). In lactating dairy goats fed ad libitum, losses in DMI due to HS stress varied between 20 and 35% according to the stage of lactation (Hamzaoui et al., 2012; 2013). In the current study, goats were non-lactating and fed at the maintenance level, so the no difference in DMI was expected. The TN goats gained 1.3 kg (+63 g/d), whereas HS goats lost 1.4 kg (-67 g/d) of BW (Table 5.3). Although they fed similar amount of DM, requirements of TN goats were well covered, whereas HS goats suffered a shortage and lost BW. It seems that maintenance requirements under HS conditions are greater than under TN conditions, and this should be taken into account in ration formulation for heat-stressed animals. The increase in maintenance requirements is necessary to cover needs for extra activities related to muscle movements for panting, greater sweating, increased chemical reactions in the body, and the production of heat shock proteins that consumes large amounts of ATP (Salama et al., 2013).

Ruminal pH and temperature

Although TN and HS goats fed the same diet and similar DMI, average rumen pH in HS was 0.12 units lower ($P < 0.01$) than in TN (Table 5.3). At all time points, pH was similar between treatments, except at 12 to 18 h post-feeding when HS goats had lower rumen pH (-0.21 ± 0.05 units; $P < 0.001$) compared to TN goats (Figure 5.8). This time interval (i.e. 12 to 18 h post-feeding) was during the night (shaded area in Figure 5.8) and it is possible that HS goats had new bouts of feeding during night hours when ambient temperature decreased from 37 to 30°C, resulting in lower rumen pH. Mishra et al. (1970), and Bandaranayaka and Holmes (1976) reported that rumen pH decreased by HS in cows fed similar amount of DM.

Rumen pH decreased by 0.51 ± 0.05 units on average at 3 h after feeding in TN and HS goats.

No TN goat had rumen pH < 6.0 , whereas only 2 HS goats had pH = 5.96 for 180 min.

Table 3. Body weight, DM and water intakes, respiration rate, rectal and rumen temperatures, and rumen pH of non-lactating goats under thermal neutral (TN, n = 8) or heat stress (HS, n = 8) conditions. Values are least squares means and SE of the difference.

Item	Treatment			Effect ($P =$)		
	TN	HS	SED	Treatment	Period	T \times P ¹
Initial BW, Kg	43.1	44.7	1.6	0.267	0.241	0.120
Final BW, Kg	44.4	43.3	1.4	0.469	0.287	0.080
BW change, kg	+1.3	-1.4	1.1	0.033	0.013	0.633
DMI, kg/d	1.13	0.98	0.10	0.183	0.944	0.971
Water consumption, L/d	2.2	5.4	0.7	0.002	0.238	0.960
Respiration rate, breaths/min	28	105	5	0.001	0.322	0.428
Rectal temperature, °C	38.6	39.0	0.1	0.001	0.276	0.134
Rumen temperature, °C	39.6	39.9	0.1	0.004	0.445	0.721
Rumen pH	6.55	6.43	0.04	0.003	0.001	0.450

¹Interaction treatment \times period.

The HS goats had greater ($+0.30^{\circ}\text{C}$; $P < 0.01$) rumen temperature than TN goats (Table 5.3) in accordance with the high ambient temperature under which HS animals were kept. Rectal temperature values were also greater ($+0.43^{\circ}\text{C}$; $P < 0.01$) in HS goats. As far as we know, rumen temperature has not been evaluated in farm animals under thermo-neutral and heat stress conditions. There was no interaction ($P = 0.998$) treatment by day hour for rumen temperature. Compared to the value before feeding, rumen temperatures increased ($P < 0.01$) by $+0.23^{\circ}\text{C}$ at 1.5 h and peaked ($+0.52^{\circ}\text{C}$; $P < 0.001$) at 8 h post-feeding, and then gradually decreased and was not significant at 16.5 h after feeding.

Figure 2 Ruminal pH (○ and ●) and ruminal temperature (△ and ▲), of non-lactating goats under thermal neutral (○, △; n = 8) or heat stress (●, ▲; n = 8) conditions. The shaded area indicates night time (2100 to 900 h) during which ambient temperature was reduced from 37 to 30 °C for heat-stressed goats. Outside this time interval, heat-stressed goats were exposed to 37 °C. The SEM values were 0.05 and 0.14 for rumen pH and temperature, respectively.

As water was freely available, no dramatic decreases in rumen temperatures have been observed (Figure 5.8) like those occurred in Exp. 1 when goats drank large amount of cold water once daily. Water temperatures were not recorded in this experiment, but their values would be similar to the ambient temperature (i.e. 20 to 23 °C for TN and 30 to 37 °C for HS). These high water temperatures, especially for HS, would cause small and hardly detectable drops in rumen temperatures.

Digestibility coefficients

Digestibility coefficients did not vary between TN and HS goats, although the HS group had numerically greater coefficients (Table 5.4). Previous results with lactating goats from the same breed fed ad libitum showed an improvement (+3 to +9 points) in the digestibility of DM, CP, NDF, and ADF (Hamzaoui et al., 2013a,b). Moreover, HS increased digestibility in male goats (Hirayama et al., 2004), dairy cows (McDowell et al., 1969), and heifers (Bernabucci et al., 1999). In all mentioned studies, feed intake decreased by HS which might explain the increment of digestibility as a consequence of depressed passage rate of the solid phase of digesta as reported by Bernabucci et al. (1999). In the current study, DMI was similar between groups, and consequently differences in digestibilities were minimal.

Blood measures

Although HS goats lost BW, they were able to maintain similar blood glucose and urea to TN goats (Table 5.5), which is similar to lactating goats fed ad libitum (Hamzaoui et al., 2013). Moreover blood pH was similar, despite the increment in respiration rate (Table 5.3). An increase in respiration rate is an important thermoregulatory response to HS, and aids in heat dissipation through evaporative cooling (Blackshaw and Blackshaw, 1994; Beatty et al. 2006). However, increased alveolar ventilation contributed to a greater loss of CO₂ in blood of HS goats (Table 5.5), shifting equilibrium HCO₃⁻ that was decreased in blood to maintain

blood pH constant. A similar mechanism has been reported in cows (Schneider et al., 1988; Calamari et al., 2007) and goats (Hamzaoui et al., 2013a).

Haematocrit and haemoglobin values were lower ($P < 0.05$) in HS than TN goats (Table 5.5). Weldy et al. (1964) reported a significant negative correlation (-0.44) between blood cell volume and rectal temperature under heat stress conditions in dairy cows. It seems that increased water consumption by HS (Table 5.3) caused hemodilution effect where more water is transported in the circulatory system for evaporative cooling.

Table 4. Digestibility coefficients of non-lactating goats under thermal neutral (TN, n = 8) or heat stress (HS, n = 8) conditions. Values are least squares means and SE of the difference.

Item	Treatment			Effect ($P =$)		
	TN	HS	SED	Treatment	Period	T × P ¹
DM	75.8	77.7	2.2	0.421	0.326	0.373
OM	78.3	79.8	2.1	0.513	0.359	0.425
CP	77.4	79.1	2.0	0.423	0.183	0.178
NDF	51.1	56.6	4.2	0.230	0.279	0.737
ADF	50.1	52.6	4.8	0.211	0.164	0.875

Table 5. Metabolic and acid-base balance indicators of non-lactating goats under thermal neutral (TN, n = 4) or heat stress (HS, n = 4) conditions. Values are least squares means and SE of the difference.

Item	Treatment		SED	Effect (<i>P</i> <)
	TN	HS		
Glucose, mg/dL	57.7	55.0	5.2	0.630
Urea, mg/dL	14.3	13.3	1.8	0.571
Na, mmol/L	149	152	1	0.021
K, nmol/L	3.47	3.83	0.30	0.292
Cl, mmol/L	111	119	2	0.017
Hematocrit, %PCV ¹	18.3	15.3	1.0	0.032
Hemoglobin, mmol/L ²	6.23	5.18	0.37	0.034
pH	7.45	7.47	0.02	0.510
Total CO ₂ , mmol/L ²	30	22	2	0.009
Anion gap, mmol/L ²	12.7	15.5	1.1	0.044
PCO ₂ , mm Hg	42	29	3	0.006
HCO ₃ ⁻ , mmol/L ²	28.8	21.1	1.8	0.007
Base excess ²	4.67	-2.75	1.97	0.013

¹Packed cell volume.

²Calculated values by the i-STAT device software.

5.4.4 Conclusions

Ruminal pH and temperature sensors record a large amount of data that could be useful to detect diurnal fluctuation of ruminal pH and temperature in relation to management and environmental changes (i.e. dietary regimen and ambient temperature). Continuous recording was helpful to measure the amount of time spent below a critical pH or temperature points, which could add further complexity to the interpretation of data. The data obtained by sensors could also reflect animal activity and changes in its behavior (i.e. feeding and drinking bouts).

By mean of these sensors, we were able to detect a lower rumen pH in heat-stressed goats, even they had similar feed intake to goats under thermal neutral conditions. This could indicate a shift in rumen fermentation and absorption of metabolites across rumen wall under heat stress conditions.